

Book of Abstracts
Slovenian Pneumology
and Allergology Congress
joined with Golnik Symposium
and Balkan Pneumology Meeting
Personalised Medicine in Respiratory
and Immunologic Diseases

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Personalised Medicine in Respiratory and Immunologic Diseases

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Glavni sponzor

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Depression-frequent comorbidity in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma

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BACKGROUND: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma are the most common chronic respiratory diseases in the working-ability population and represents serious public health problem both in developed and developing countries. Both diseases are associated with numerous comorbidities, including depression which leads to frequent use of health services, increases duration of hospitalization and causes poorer control of COPD and asthma.

The aim of this study: was to determine the frequency and degree of depression in patients with COPD and asthma; to determine whether there is a correlation between the severity of COPD and the frequency and level of depression; to determine whether there is a correlation between the level of asthma control and the frequency and level of depression; to determine whether there is a difference in the frequency and level of depression among patients with COPD, patients with asthma and healthy population.

METHODS: The study included total of 500 individuals (200 with asthma and 200 with COPD) who were referred for control check-up and 100 healthy individuals who were in the control group.

RESULTS: In patients with asthma, depression is registered in 14.5 %. In patients with COPD, depression is registered in 23.5%. Patients with poorly controlled asthma are significantly more often depressed and have higher degree of depression than patients with controlled asthma ($p < 0.001$). Patients with more severe level of COPD are significantly more frequently depressed and their level of depression is more severe than in patients with milder degree of COPD ($p < 0.001$). Patients with COPD are significantly more likely to have depression, that is of higher level than in patients with asthma ($p < 0.001$) or compared to healthy subjects ($p < 0.001$). Patients with asthma are significantly more likely to have depression, which is of more serious level than in the healthy subjects ($p = 0.002$). Multivariate logistic regression was associated with each factor weight value and calculated the statistical significance of the impact of each factor on the occurrence of depression.

CONCLUSION: Independent predictors of depression in a group of patients with asthma were: age, smoking habits and uncontrolled asthma. An independent predictors of depression in a group of patients with COPD are the total number of hospitalizations and dyspnea degree higher than one.